

Airborne transport and characterization of microalgal bioaerosols generated in raceway and tubular photobioreactors

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Abstract

The increasing demand for natural products has attracted special attention to microalgal biomass, which is often cultivated in open ponds. These systems are vulnerable to biological contamination, which reduces both the yield and quality of the biomass. The contamination process, particularly through airborne transport of unwanted microalgae, fungi, or bacteria, is poorly understood. In this study, bioaerosols were collected in quartz filters through a low-volume sampler located at different locations at the CIESOL demonstration plant (Almeria, Spain). The samples were analysed using metagenomics and SEM-EDS to assess the number of cells and the microbial diversity of the filters. The results revealed airborne transport of microalgae across different locations, with a gradual decrease in cell numbers as the distance from the source increased ($p < 0.05$). Additionally, although different microalgal strains were detected in the filters, the most abundant belonged to the *Chlorella* family. The results obtained from this research highlight how microalgae and other bioaerosols can travel over various distances from the original source, with the potential to contaminate open ponds and even closed photobioreactors.

Keywords: microalgae, bioaerosols, airborne transport, contamination

1. Introduction

The term microalgae refers to photosynthetic microorganisms including prokaryotic cyanobacteria and eukaryotic microalgae. These microorganisms are gaining increased interest because of their rich nutritional composition (proteins, amino acids, minerals, vitamins, etc.) and content in high-value bioactive compounds (polyunsaturated fatty acids, phycobiliproteins, carotenoids, etc.) [1]. Some of latter have demonstrated antifungal, antiviral, antioxidation or antibiotic properties [2]. All these aspects have contributed to the rapid growth of the microalgae market, with microalgal biomass showing potential in multiple industries including food [3], agriculture [4], aquaculture [5], pharmacy [2,6], and climate change mitigation [7]. The global microalgae market is projected to reach USD 4.6 billion by 2027 [8].

Microalgal biomass is mainly produced using open ponds (OP). Compared to closed photobioreactors, these systems have lower construction and operating costs as well as energy consumption [9,10]. At the commercial scale, the most widely used open ponds are raceways. Raceways have been used for decades to produce microalgae. However, they have one major limitation: they can only be used to produce strains that are either extremophile or extremely fast-growing. The reason for this is that, in raceways, the culture is in direct contact with the environment and is therefore vulnerable to external contamination. The main contaminants include bacteria, fungi, viruses and zooplankton that limit the growth of the target strain or even lead to a culture crash within a few days [11,12]. Other microalgal strains can also contaminate the culture and eventually take over the culture. For example, a metagenomic analysis carried out in a recent study aiming to produce the microalgae *Anabaena* and *Dolichospermum*

revealed that *Chlorella*, which was being produced in a large reactor nearby, was the most abundant eukaryote in the culture [13]. Furthermore, a metagenomic analysis revealed that *Nitzschia* sp. was the most abundant microalga in an open bioreactor that was inoculated with *Scenedesmus almeriensis* approximately one month earlier [14]. The growth of unwanted microorganisms represents a challenge to large-scale microalgae producers.

Biological contamination in open ponds can occur through multiple mechanisms. These include birds, aquatic insects, rodents, and airborne transport (bioaerosols) [15]. The use of greenhouses to cover raceway reactors has been investigated as a strategy to reduce the contact of the culture with animals including insects and birds [16]. However, bioaerosols are more challenging as different strains might be produced inside one same greenhouse, and the installation of a greenhouse represents an extra cost that not all the microalgae producers are willing to pay. Other strategies including water filtration or selective adjustment of the culture conditions are also used to limit the appearance of unwanted microorganisms. For example, the use of sodium bicarbonate at high concentrations is a common strategy followed by producers of *Spirulina*. This microalga has a high tolerance to alkaline media and a preferential uptake of bicarbonate [17]. However, even reactors inoculated with extremophile strains can be contaminated with unwanted microorganisms. For example, *Alkalimonas* sp. and *Lentimonas* sp. as well as an unclassified metazoan have recently been identified in cultures of *Spirulina* [18].

Although the airborne transport of microorganisms has been previously studied [19–21], no studies exist on the characterisation of bioaerosols produced in microalgae production facilities. For this reason, the aim of this work was to

assess, for the first time, the transport of microalgae from the two most common photobioreactors being used today: raceways and tubular reactors. The former generally includes a paddlewheel, where bioaerosols can be easily generated [22,23]. In the latter, despite being closed to the environment, bioaerosols can be easily produced in the bubble column that is used to provide carbon dioxide and remove excess oxygen. Different sampling points were considered and the amount of microalgal cells in the air was monitored using metagenomic analyses and microscopic observations.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study location and sampling

The study was conducted from 14 November 2024 to 27 January 2025 at the CIESOL demonstration plant, located at the University of Almería (Spain). This study focused on the two major sites where bioaerosols were being produced:

- (i) The paddlewheel of a 600 m² raceway reactor, which was located right before a 5 m³ sump where air was continuously injected at a flow rate of 350 L·min⁻¹. This photobioreactor was initially inoculated with *Scenedesmus almeriensis*.
- (ii) A 250 L bubble column attached to a 3.6 m² tubular reactor where air was continuously injected at a flow rate of 80 L·min⁻¹. This photobioreactor was initially inoculated with *Chlorella sorokiniana*.

The raceway reactor was located outdoors while the tubular photobioreactor was located inside a greenhouse which was completely sealed (Figure 1). It is important to highlight that inside the greenhouse there were also three 100 L

bubble columns bubbling air at a constant rate of 15 L·min⁻¹. These columns contained a culture dominated by *Scenedesmus almeriensis*.

The biological samples were collected at different sampling points shown in Figure 1 and described below:

Outdoor sampling points:

- (1) 1 m away from the paddlewheel and the sump of the raceway reactor and 1.5 m elevated from the ground.
- (2) 10 m away from the paddlewheel and the sump of the raceway reactor and 1.5 m elevated from the ground.
- (3) 30 m away from the paddlewheel and the sump of the raceway reactor and 1.5 m elevated from the ground.
- (4) 400 m away from the paddlewheel and the sump of the raceway reactor and 10 m elevated from the ground. For cell concentration analysis, sampling point 4 was considered the control sample.

Indoor sampling points:

- (5) 50 m away from the paddlewheel and the sump of the raceway reactor and 1.5 m elevated from the ground. This sampling point was inside a building with offices and laboratories.
- (6) 5 m away from the bubble column of the tubular photobioreactor and 1.5 m elevated from the ground. This sampling point was inside a greenhouse that was completely sealed. As mentioned before, two different strains were being produced inside the greenhouse.

At each location, biological samples were collected in triplicate using circular quartz filters (47 mm diameter, Pallflex) over 2.4-h and 24-h time periods (starting

at 9:00 AM local time). Sampling was done using a LVS 3.1 low volume sampler (Comde-Derenda, Stahnsdorf, Germany; $2.3 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$) at a height of 1.5 m above ground level. Sampling was carried out on days with similar climatic conditions (mainly wind speed). To prevent external biological contamination, filter samples were stored before and after sampling in sealed Petri dishes and handled using tweezers and single-use nitrile gloves, as performed in previous work [24–26]. Additionally, blank filters were also analysed.

2.2 Cell concentration

The quantification of microalgal cells was done using a Leica DM 750 microscope coupled with a Flexacam i5 camera (Leica Microsystemas, Barcelona, Spain) and using Enersight software (Leica Microsystemas, Barcelona, Spain). At each location, individual cells within an area of $12,000 \mu\text{m}^2$ were counted in 15 different regions of each filter. Because of the large concentration of particles in the 24-h filters, the microscopic quantification of cells was done using the 2.4-h filters. The average and total number of cells per μm^2 were then determined and the cell concentration per m^3 of air was calculated.

2.3 Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM)

The 24-h filters were analysed by FESEM to study the chemical composition, size, and shape of individual biological particles. FESEM measurements were carried out using a Zeiss Sigma 300 VP Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope with an attached energy-dispersive X-ray (EDS) analyser (Oxford Instruments). Filter fragments were covered by a thin layer of conductive carbon (5–10 nm) under vacuum conditions (10^{-7} mbar). Magnification ranged from 500 to 60,000 X, and the accelerating voltage was set at 5-10 kV.

2.4 Metagenomic analysis

The prokaryotic and eukaryotic diversity in the 24-h filters was analysed by Stab Vida, Lda. (Lisbon, Portugal). The molecular markers used were 18S rDNA - V9 (V8F and 1510R) and 16S V3-V4 (16S_F(341F) and 16S_R(785R)) for eukaryotes and prokaryotes, respectively. The DNA extraction was done using a Maxwell® RSC PureFood GMO and Authentication Kit (Promega Biotech Iberica SL, Madrid, Spain) and sequencing was carried out on the Illumina MiSeq platform with the MiSeq Reagent Kit v3, generating 300 bp paired-end reads. The raw sequence data were processed and analysed using QIIME2 (2024.2 version).

2.5 Air-mass trajectory modeling

The potential trajectories of microalgae bioaerosols generated from the paddlewheel of the raceway reactor from 14 November 2024 to 27 January 2025 were obtained by using HYSPLIT (Hybrid Single Particle Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory) backward and forward trajectories [27] on the READY website (<https://www.ready.noaa.gov>) and the GDAS (Global Data Assimilation System) 1-degree meteorological data.

2.6 Statistical analysis

All the analytical determinations were done in triplicate per natural replicate except stated otherwise. Six filters (3 after filtering during 2.4 h and 3 after filtering during 24 h) were obtained in each sampling point, being each filter the experimental unit. Differences between locations were analysed by analysis of variance (ANOVA) and a Fisher's least significant difference (LSD). A significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ was used.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Cell concentration

The concentration of microalgae cells in the air ($\text{cells}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) at the different sampling points, both outdoors and indoors, is shown in Figure 2. The distance of the sampling point to the paddlewheel of the reactor had a significant effect on the cell concentration ($p<0.05$). A gradual decrease in cell concentration was observed as the distance from the source increased. This pattern can be explained by the dry deposition of microalgae particles greater than $10\ \mu\text{m}$, as pointed out by previous studies [22]. For instance, the highest cell concentration was observed at location 1 ($2.42\text{E}+11\ \text{cells}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$; 1 m away from the paddlewheel), followed by location 2 ($1.45\text{E}+11\ \text{cells}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$; 10 m away from the paddlewheel), and location 3 ($1.13\text{E}+11\ \text{cells}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$; 30 m away from the paddlewheel). Although location 4, located 400 m away from the paddlewheel, showed a lower cell concentration compared to the previous sampling points, a significant number of cells were detected ($1.97\text{E}+10\ \text{cells}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$). When considering location 4 as the control sample for cell concentration measurements, the cell concentration in the air sampled at locations 1, 2, and 3 showed increases of 1128, 636, and 474%, respectively. This demonstrates the extremely high concentration of microalgae cells in the air surrounding raceway reactors. To the best authors knowledge, the results reported in this study confirm, for the first time, airborne transport of microalgae from open ponds across different locations.

The high cell density in the air close to raceway reactors could not just represent a health hazard but also a challenge because of the capacity of these microalgae

to take over cultures being produced nearby. Indeed, previous studies suggested that the appearance of unwanted microalgae in open ponds might be attributed to aerial transport. For example, two raceway reactors inoculated with *Anabaena* sp. or *Dolichospermum* sp. were recently contaminated with cells of *Chlorella* that were being produced in a large reactor located nearby [13]. In this study, airborne microalgae transport was detected up to 30 m from the original source (paddlewheel). However, microalgae have the potential to travel and reach longer distances, like other aerosols and bioaerosols [28,29]. For this reason, it is likely that the cells collected 400 m away from the raceway came from other emitting point; for example, the Mediterranean Sea that is relatively close.

A high cell concentration was also quantified in both indoor locations (5 and 6). Sampling location 5, located inside a building containing offices and laboratories, was 50 m from the original source (the paddlewheel). The cell concentration at this site ($6.37E+10$ cells·m⁻³) was lower when compared to the sampling points located outdoors (sampling points 1, 2, and 3) ($p<0.05$). This was expected as this sampling point was inside a building. However, the number of cells in the air indoors was high, even higher than that obtained at the outdoor location 4 ($p<0.05$). These findings indicate airborne transport of microalgae from outdoor sources even in indoor atmospheres. It is important to highlight that despite being indoors, the building's doors are generally open with several researchers entering and exiting the building during the whole day. Sources of indoor bioaerosols have been extensively studied in the literature, including outdoor air, human activities, suspended particles, and ventilation systems [30–33]. In the present study, the main source of indoor airborne microalgae was the outdoor air.

Sampling location 6 is different from the previously described ones. In this case, the sampling was done inside a greenhouse, 5 m away from the 250 L bubble column of a tubular photobioreactor. The reactor was being used to produce *Chlorella sorokiniana*, but three bubble columns were being used to produce *Scenedesmus almeriensis* inside the same greenhouse. Although tubular photobioreactors are closed systems, the cell concentration at this site ($2.31\text{E}+11$ cells·m⁻³) was higher than at all outdoor locations, except for location 1 (1 m away from the paddlewheel) ($p<0.05$). This elevated cell concentration can be explained by two key factors. In the first place, because the bubble column of the tubular photobioreactor acted as a source of aerosols. Air was being continuously bubbled at the bottom of the column. In the second place, because of the closed environment inside the greenhouse, where the ventilation with outdoor air was limited, leading to the accumulation of airborne microalgae.

3.2 Metagenomic analyses

Figure 3 shows the microbial diversity of the eukaryotic populations in the air across the six different sampling points. Fungi were the dominant group in the bioaerosols at all locations (Figure 3A). One of the most abundant fungal genera identified in the air was *Cladosporium*, a common fungal allergen known for releasing mycotoxins [34]. The “Other” group included taxa from the phyla Phragmoplastophyta, Vertebrata, Aphelidea, Animalia, among others. Figure 4B further confirms the high cell concentration of microalgae in both indoor locations (locations 5 and 6). The results described herein highlight the relevance of airborne fungal contamination. However, the study of fungi is outside the scope of this study which focused on investigating airborne contamination and transport of microalgae.

Regarding microalgae diversity, it is important to highlight that the open raceway pond was initially inoculated with *Scenedesmus almeriensis*. Figure 4 shows the taxonomic classification of airborne microalgae diversity at different sampling locations at the phylum, class, family, and genus level. At the phylum level (Figure 4A), *Chlorophyta* was the predominant phylum across all outdoor locations. This phylum includes microalgae such as *Scenedesmus* and *Chlorella*, which were the main genera being produced at the moment of sampling. As distance from the aerosol source (the paddlewheel) increased, the abundance of the phylum *Chlorophyta* declined, while the presence of the phylum *Ochrophyta*, which includes the genus *Ochromonas*, became more evident. This genus of unicellular, flagellated algae is especially interesting because of being mixotrophic microorganisms and their ability to accumulate carotenoids. Interestingly, no trace of the genus *Ochromonas* was detected at location 4 (400 m away from the paddlewheel) suggesting that its source was within the CIESOL facility where the study was conducted. In both indoor locations, *Chlorophyta* was also the predominant phylum. At location 5, several additional phyla were observed at relatively low abundances. These included *Diatomea*, *Cercozoa*, and *Ochrophyta*. These findings confirm that both outdoor air and human activity contribute to the indoor microalgal diversity inside the building. At location 6, alongside *Chlorophyta*, small amounts of *Ochrophyta* and *Diatomea* were present, indicating that microalgae from outside can also infiltrate closed environments like greenhouses. These results demonstrate the complexity of avoiding contamination with unwanted strains as bioaerosols can reach even closed environments.

At the class level (Figure 4B), the dominant group in outdoor samples was *Trebouxiophyceae*, which includes the genus *Chlorella*, followed by *Chlorophyceae*, and *Chlorodendrophyceae*. The abundance of *Trebouxiophyceae* decreased with increasing distance from the aerosol source, especially in locations 1, 2, and 3, indicating that the primary source of *Chlorella* aerosols was the open raceway pond. *Chlorella* was not being the main cultivated genus in the raceway, which suggests that that the genus *Chlorella* forms bioaerosols more easily than genus *Scenedesmus*. The main reason might be the morphology of the cells. While *Chlorella* cells are spherical (or round to slightly oval) and are small (generally 2-10 μm), *Scenedesmus* cells are typically ellipsoidal, ovoid, fusiform, or cylindrical, are a bit larger (5-50 μm) and form colonies of 2, 4, or 8 cells arranged in a linear row further increasing their size. Nevertheless, bioaerosols from the classes *Chlorophyceae* and *Chrysophyceae* (as seen in locations 1 and 3) and *Bacillariophyceae* (detected in location 2 in smaller amounts) were also identified. Location 4 showed a relatively high abundance of *Trebouxiophyceae*, followed by *Chlorophyceae* and *Mediophyceae*, again confirming the easier aerial dispersion of *Chlorella* when compared with *Scenedesmus*. For the indoor locations, location 5 was dominated by *Chlorophyceae*, followed by *Trebouxiophyceae* and a variety of other classes including *Chlorodendrophyceae*. This suggests that aerosol transmission and human activity both contribute to the diversity observed within the building. At location 6, the most abundant classes were *Trebouxiophyceae* (associated with *Chlorella* cultivated in the tubular photobioreactors) and *Chlorophyceae* (associated with *Scenedesmus almeriensis* cultivated in bubble columns). Small

amounts of *Chrysophyceae* (*Ochromonadales*) and *Coscinodiscophytina* (*Diatomea*) were also detected.

At the family and genus levels (Figure 4C and D), location 1 was dominated by the family *Chlorellales*, confirming that the paddlewheel is a major source of *Chlorella* bioaerosols. Additionally, smaller proportions of microalgae from the family *Sphaeropleales* (genera *Scenedesmus* and *Desmodesmus*) and genus *Picochlorum* were present. Location 2 also showed high abundance of *Chlorellales*, along with the genus *Picochlorum*, family *Bacillariophyceae*, and *Sphaeropleales* (*Desmodesmus*). At location 3, *Chlorellales* remained dominant, followed by the families *Ochromonadales* (*Ochromonas*), *Chrysophyceae*, and *Sphaeropleales* (*Scenedesmus*). These results further confirm the aerial transport of *Chlorella* aerosols, and to a lesser extent *Scenedesmus* and *Desmodesmus*. The genera *Ochromonas* and *Chrysophyceae* appear to originate from the CIESOL facility, as previously noted. At location 4, in addition to the family *Chlorellales*, the genera *Picochlorum*, *Chloroidium*, *Chlamydomonas*, *Thalassiosira*, and *Trebouxiophyceae* were detected. In indoor location 5, the most abundant family was *Sphaeropleales* (*Desmodesmus* and *Scenedesmus*), followed by *Chlorellales* and the genus *Picochlorum*, confirming that aerosols from the open raceway reactor reach indoor spaces. Finally, at indoor location 6, the most abundant families were *Chlorellales* and *Sphaeropleales* (*Desmodesmus* and *Scenedesmus*), confirming that aerosols from *Chlorella* and *Scenedesmus/Desmodesmus* originated from the tubular photobioreactor, and the bubble columns located inside the greenhouse.

Overall, the results obtained from this research provide evidence of long-range transport of microalgae through aerosols from the original source, representing a potential source of contamination for open and closed-system photobioreactors.

3.3 FESEM measurements

Individual particles retained in the filters were analysed using FESEM. These analyses confirmed the presence of individual microalgal cells in all the six sampling locations. Different microalgal strains were observed (Figure 5). Among the microalgae identified, strains belonging to the genera *Scenedesmus* and *Chlorella* were visually identified. *Scenedesmus* strains are generally ellipsoidal or cylindrical (5-50 μm length, 2-10 μm width) and form non-motile coenobial colonies consisting of 2, 4, or sometimes 8 cells arranged linearly [35]. In turn, *Chlorella* cells are spherical or nearly spherical in shape typically 2-10 μm in diameter [36]. Figure 5A provides a general overview of the different individual particles captured within the fibres of a filter obtained at location 1. At this location, because of its proximity, the paddlewheel was the primary source of aerosol particles, resulting in the presence of multiple particle types including microalgae and salts. Additionally, it was frequently observed that microalgal cells were covered by salts such as CaCO_3 , NaCl , or a combination of both. These salts are present in the culture medium. The detection of silicon (Si) in all the samples is attributed to the silicic nature of the filter.

Figure 5B shows an individual cell and its corresponding elemental spectrum at location 4 (outdoor location 400 m away). The primary components of the cell were, as expected, carbon, oxygen, and nitrogen. Similarly, Figure 5C illustrates an individual cell and its corresponding spectrum at the indoor location 6. In this

case, the cell composition differed slightly from the previous, suggesting that it was a different strain. While the culture being produced in the open raceway pond was a polyculture initially inoculated with *Scenedesmus almeriensis*, the tubular reactor (that was the main source of aerosols inside the greenhouse, was being used to produce *Chlorella sorokiniana*. *Chlorella* strains were the most abundant in the air inside the greenhouse. Therefore, it is likely that the cell analysed in location 6 was a cell of *Chlorella*, most likely *Chlorella sorokiniana*. Finally, Figure 5D shows an individual cell along with its spectrum. The cell shown in Figure 5D was collected from air at the indoor sampling location 5. The cell was covered with CaCO_3 , as confirmed by the elemental composition given by the spectrum. Microalgae can remove salts from the culture medium by two mechanisms: absorption, a metabolism dependent process where salts are absorbed into the cells and adsorption, a non-metabolism process related to the physical adherence of ions and molecules onto the cell wall. Indeed, some microalgae including *Scenedesmus obliquus* have been used in biological desalination processes to remove salts mainly by adsorption (REF). Microalgae from the genus *Chlorella* have also been used to adsorb heavy metals such as cadmium in a process that is highly dependent on the functional group composition of the outer cell wall (REF).

Overall, the results obtained from FESEM confirm the presence of individual microalgae particles in air. Most of these cells were covered or partially covered with salts that were being used in the culture medium of the different photobioreactors.

3.4 Air-mass forward trajectories

4. Conclusions

In this study, airborne transport of microalgae from the two most common photobioreactors (raceways and tubular reactors) was investigated. Bioaerosols were collected on quartz filters at various indoor and outdoor locations at the CIESOL demonstration plant (Almeria, Spain) and characterised using metagenomics and SEM-EDS.

Cell concentration results revealed, for the first time, airborne transport of microalgae across different locations, with a progressively decrease in concentration as the distance from the original source (open raceway reactor) increased. Additionally, cell concentrations at indoor locations were particularly high, highlighting the role of closed systems, such as tubular photobioreactors and vertical columns, as significant sources of microalgae bioaerosols.

Metagenomic analysis confirmed the presence of various strains of microalgae at all locations, particularly from the genus *Chlorella*, due to its small cell size. Finally, SEM-EDS analysis enabled the visualization of individual microalgae particles and confirmed that these cells were covered with salts originating from the culture medium.

The results obtained from this research reveal, for the first time how microalgae and other bioaerosols can travel over various distances from the original source

in microalgae facilities. These findings confirm that the paddlewheels of raceways and the bubbling columns of tubular reactors act as sources of bioaerosols, with the potential to contaminate other cultures.

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Declaration of interests

The authors have no conflict of interests to declare

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Marina-Montes, C.: Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Visualization, Writing – original draft; Lafarga, T.: Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Writing – original draft; Funding acquisition; Anzano, J.: Resources; Ación, G.: Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing.

Figure legends:

Figure 1. Location of the different sampling points within the CIESOL Demonstration Plant and the University of Almería. The red marker shows the exact position of the sampling point. Images were taken from Google Earth Pro (CA, USA).

Figure 2. Microalgae cell concentration (number of cells·m⁻³) in the air at the different sampling points. Values represent the mean of three independent determinations ± SD.

Figure 3. (A) Relative abundance (%) of microbial groups identified at the different sampling points and (B) comparison of the relative abundance of microbial groups between indoor and outdoor environments.

Figure 4. Taxonomic classification of the eukaryotic populations in the air at the different locations at the (A) phylum, (B) class, (C) family, and (D) genus level.

Figure 5. (A) General overview of various individual particles, including microalgal cells, at location 1 under FESEM analysis; (B) Microalgal cell FESEM image at location 4, with its corresponding spectrum; (C) Microalgae cell FESEM image at location 6, with its corresponding

spectrum; and (D) Microalgal cell FESEM image at location 5, with its corresponding spectrum.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

References

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